

ATTITUDE OF COLLEGE GIRL STUDENTS TOWARDS THEIR EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The present study was examined on the Girl students' attitude towards education. The present was focused on the domestic affairs and marital obligations of girl students in Gangtok city of Sikkim State. An educated girl can share the load and burden of the men in different fields. Education of girls is now considered as the awakening of girls in the modern era. Educated girls are more likely to get a job, earn money and they can live independently and also they can financially support their family. Girls are now competing with boys in all the spheres of life. But still, there are some people who oppose girl's education because they believe that a girl's sphere is at home and also they think that it is wastage of money spend on girls' education. The data collected from 120 girl students from 2 selected colleges by using questionnaire namely "Attitude of Girls towards Education" by Deepika and Raju (2020). The study is a quantitative method and the data was collected by using the questionnaire. The study was conducted on both private and Government Institutions on different stream of students. The results shown that, significant differences were found between private and Government colleges and also in different streams.

Keywords: Attitude, Parental Encouragement, Teachers Support, Academic Achievement

Introduction

In psychology, attitude is a psychological construct, a mental and emotional entity that inheres in, or characterizes a person. They are complex and are an acquired state through experiences. It is an individual's predisposed state of mind regarding a value and it is precipitated through a responsive expression towards oneself, a person, place, things, or event which in turn influences the individual's thought and action. An attitude is an organization of concepts, beliefs, motives, habits, and acts associated with a particular object. The concept and beliefs associated with an attitude are referred to as the cognitive component; the habits, as the action component; and the motives, as the affective component, we say that an attitude is formed when

the above components are so interrelated that specific feelings, emotions and reaction tendencies become consistently associated with a particular way of thinking about certain persons or events.

An attitude is a positive; negative or mixed evaluation of an object that is expressed at same level of intensity. It is an expression of a favorable or unfavorable evaluation of a person, place, things, or event. These are fundamental determinants of our perceptions of, and actions towards all aspects of our social environment. Attitudes involve a complex organization of evaluative beliefs, feelings, and tendencies toward certain actions.

Kiran Mor, Savneet Sethia (2016) conducted a study on "Parent's Attitude towards Girls Education in Haryana", this was conducted

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in Haryana. This paper examines the extent of parent's attitude on education of different group of population in the region of Haryana. The study was carried on the data 600 parents out of these 280 parents' belonged to rural areas and 317 families' belonged to urban areas of Haryana. A 25- item questionnaire was used for collecting data along with personal interview. The findings showed that the overall attitude of the respondents was moderately favorable and positive towards education of their child. The results also indicated that there was no significant difference in the attitude of rural and urban parents. Gender difference was also found to be non-significant.

Ishmirekha Handique Konwar (2017) examined the attitude of college students towards e-learning. Secondly, to study the difference in attitude of college students towards e-learning with regards to gender and the third is to study the difference in attitude of college students towards e-learning with regards to locality. Sample of 200 college students were randomly selected. It was found that both male and female students possess high attitude towards e-learning but female students have slightly higher attitude towards e-learning than male college students. And also both rural and urban students possess high attitude towards e-learning but urban students have slightly higher attitude towards e-learning than rural college students.

Tomba Chingthan, Tinkhoiling Guite (2017) conducted a study on "Parental Attitude towards girl's education", this was conducted in Senapati District Manipur. The population for the study was confined to the parents of girl's child in the Senapati district of Manipur. Sampling procedures provide generalization on the basis of a relatively small proportion of the population. The sample for the study consists of 100 parents, out of which 50 will be from urban and 50 will be from rural areas of Senapati district of Manipur. The simple random sampling method is applied for the study. From the result of the research the Urban, it is observed that parents have more understanding about the necessity of education and its impact on being a good citizen than the rural parents. The methodological framework of this study was descriptive survey method.

Susantakar et.al (2018) conducted a study on "Attitude of Post Graduate students towards sustainable development", this was conducted in Burdwan district, West Bengal. Sample of the study was 100 PG students under Burdwan district. The survey method and stratified random sampling technique has been used in selecting the sample. The means, standard deviation, t-test, ANOVA has been applied for the interpretation of findings. The result shows that students have high attitude towards sustainable development and there is no significant interaction between student's gender, residence and stream of study.

Nilofer Jan, Neerja Sharma (2019) examined on "Parental attitude towards girl's education: A case study in Jahangirabad, Bhopal", which was conducted in Jahangirabad, Bhopal. The data was collected from 100 parent respondents (both male and female) for knowing their attitude towards girl's education. The results indicated that parents majority (43%) of the girls in Jahangirabad are very poor whose income fall in the range of 5001-10000 Rs. Per month. Further highest number of male parents (37%) was labors and maximum numbers of female parents (88%) were housewives while as only one among them was found as government employee. Education level of the highest number of male parents (29%) was secondary while as lowest number of male parents (11%) was primary. Similarly in case of female parents, data indicated the education level of the highest percentage of female parents (15%) was secondary while as lowest percentage of female parents (7%) was post-graduation.

Sudip Mandal, et.al (2019) conducted a study on "Attitudes of graduate students towards higher studies". Indian higher studies have never accepted much eminence when compared to the primary level. Academicians of our country have already pointed out that for economic and social well-being of our country majorly depends on the quality and prevalent of higher studies in our country. The main hindrance is the misconceptions by the general public of our country which is accompanied by the economic issues. The vision of Ministry of Human Resource and Development heads the department of Higher Education whose aim is to realize India's human resource prospective to its fullest in the education sector,

with equity and excellence. Higher studies is a precious affair when we take into consideration the fact that almost 20% of the population still lie under the poverty line. There is still a gap in the level of enrolment between males and females.

The government is trying hard to overcome this disparity. Skills have often been ignored in our country's scenario. Thus, higher studies should also promote and encourage technical education. An All India Survey on Higher Education was initiated only in 2011, only because none of the origins had a complete picture of the data on higher studies. A large amount of population is also a problem as it becomes difficult to provide to the needs of each individual or group. The resources are meager when compared to the people demanding for it. We should try to recognize the problems, and then we should work towards solving those problems. Public of our country should be keen to send their children for higher studies; they should be having a positive attitude towards higher studies.

Indian Government, both at the central and state level have taken conscious effort to promote education for the girl child. All children are entitled to free education till class VIII under the Right to Education Act. To address the declining sex ratio and to raise awareness regarding the importance of girl education, Prime Minister Narendra Modi launched the Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao Scheme. Several state Governments provide free education for girl child, free textbooks, educational loan, Sukanya Samridhi Yojna and many other policies to help girl child obtain a formal education.

Research in girls education related issues have revealed that today's girls education generate an impression that girl education has been improved. But in reality, girls still suffer from social and economic oppression and discrimination at homes, school and work place. A well educated and grown up girl can play an important role in the development of the country. An educated girl can share the load and burden of the men in different fields. Education of girls is now considered as the awakening of girls in the modern era. Educated girls are more likely to get a job, earn money and they can live independently

and also they can financially support their family. Girls are now competing with boys in all the spheres of life. But still, there are some people who oppose girl's education because they believe that a girl's sphere is at home and also they think that it is wastage of money to spend on girls' education. This thought is wrong as girl education can bring an uprising in the culture.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the attitude of college girl students towards their education in relation to stream variations (Arts, Science and Commerce).
- To study the attitude of college girls' students towards their education in relation to nature of institutions (government and private).

Hypotheses:

- There will be no significant difference in the attitude of college girl students towards their education in relation to stream variations.
- There will be no significant difference in the attitude of college girl students towards their education in relation to nature of institution.

METHOD

Sample of respondents

The study was conducted on a sample of 120 girl students from selected colleges from Gangtok city of Sikkim state. The sample consists of 120 girls' students, 40 graduate girl students from each stream (Science, Commerce, Arts). The sample of the study was limited to 120 college girls students out of which 60 were from government college and 60 were from private college in an around Gangtok. The data were collected by way of random sampling technique. Thus the total sample of 120 was adequate to test the hypotheses in the above mentioned variables.

Tools

Keeping in the view of the objectives of the study and also the nature of research, the standardized tool 'Attitude scale for girls'

education' developed by Deepika and Raju (2020) was used for the present study

Procedure

Attitude scale for girls' education' developed by Deepika and Raju (2020) was selected to suit the specific needs of the present study as well as the sample to be investigated. The researcher approached the two colleges among two one from private and another from government college and got the permission from principals of the colleges. The preliminary information sheet, Attitude scale for girls' education was given to

graduate girls students and they were asked to fill the preliminary information and the attitude scale as per the instructions given in the scale.

Statistical analysis

The descriptive statistical technique was used after the collection of the data in the present study. The important statistical measures mostly used were Mean, SD, t-test, was done in order to test the significant difference between the students of Government and Private institution. The scores were analyzed with the help of computer and used SPSS package for analysing the data.

Results and Discussion

Table-1: Showing the comparison of attitude of college girl students towards their education in government and private colleges.

Dimension	Management	Mean	SD	t-value
Parental Encouragement	Government	14.47	0.99	1.61
	Private	14.72	0.66	
Teachers Support	Government	13.88	1.38	3.22
	Private	14.6	1.03	
School/college Facilities	Government	12.68	2.35	0.72
	Private	12.38	2.21	
Academic Achievement	Government	12.13	2.3	2.73
	Private	13.3	2.37	
Individual Interest	Government	14.53	0.76	0.75
	Private	14.42	0.92	
Role of Girl	Government	13.25	1.42	0.77
	Private	13.45	1.41	
Total Attitude	Government	80.95	5.99	1.8
	Private	82.87	5.64	

The mean scores, SD and t-value of the total dimensions of attitude of college girls students towards their education in Government and Private colleges, were incorporated in table-1. It can be understood that Parental encouragement in studies, School facilities, Individual interest and role of girls were not statistically significant. So the hypotheses framed related to these dimensions were accepted.

The other dimensions like Teachers support, Academic achievement and Total attitude were statistically significant. The Null hypotheses framed for Teachers support dimension between Government and Private Colleges was rejected and the value is highly significant. Another dimension Academic achievement between Government and Private College students was also rejected and the value is highly significant. The total attitude between Government and Private College girl students was rejected and the value is significant.

Table-2: Showing the comparison of Attitude of college girl students towards their Education among Arts, Science and Commerce.

(Arts=40, Science=40, Commerce=40)

Dimensions	Stream	Mean	SD	F-Values
Parental Encouragement	Arts	14.68	0.76	1.53
	Science	14.4	0.92	
	Commerce	14.7	0.85	
Teachers Support	Arts	14.28	1.24	0.08
	Science	14.18	1.25	
	commerce	14.28	1.32	
School/college Facilities	Arts	11.68	2.26	4.54
	Science	12.9	1.86	
	Commerce	13.03	2.46	
Academic Achievement	Arts	13.1	2.25	0.77
	Science	12.48	1.94	
	Commerce	12.58	2.91	
Individual Interest	Arts	14.3	0.96	2.81
	Science	14.73	0.67	
	Commerce	14.4	0.84	
Role of Girl	Arts	13.48	1.3	1.13
	Science	13.08	1.36	
	Commerce	13.5	1.56	
Total Attitude	Arts	81.5	5.6	0.29
	Science	81.75	5.38	
	Commerce	82.48	6.93	

From the above table indicate the Mean scores, SD, and t-value of the total dimensions of attitude of college girls students towards education among Arts, Science and Commerce in government and private colleges were incorporated in the table-2. It can be understood

that Parental encouragement, teachers support, academic achievement, role of a girl and total attitude were not statistically significant. So that hypothesis framed related to these dimensions were accepted.

The other dimensions like School facilities, Individual interest were statistically significant. The Null hypothesis framed for School facilities dimension among Arts, Science and Commerce stream of government and private colleges was rejected and the value is highly significant. Another dimension Individual interest among Arts, Science and Commerce stream of government and private college girls' student was also rejected and the value is highly significant. The Total attitude among Arts, Science and Commerce was accepted and the value is statistically not significant.

Conclusion

Research in girls education related issues have revealed that today's girls education generate an impression that girls' education has been improved. A well educated and grown up girl can play an important role in the development of the country. The main purpose of this study is to study the attitude of college girls' students towards their education in relation to nature of institution. The researcher found that there is no significance difference between government and private college girl students towards their education. Another purpose of the study is to study the attitude of college girls' students towards their education in relation to stream variations. The researcher found that there is no significant difference among attitude of college girls students towards their education in relation to stream variations.

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